

TRANSLATION SYSTEMS AND MACHINE TRANSLATION

Khasanxonova Durdonakhon Juraxon qizi

Student of SamSIFL

ANNOTATION

In this article were discussed the relevance of the study is due to the need to clarify the strategies for the implementation of special translation in accordance with the communicative-functional approach to translation. The question of the dependence of the degree to which the content of the text is reproduced in translation depends on the characteristics of the communicative situation and the chosen strategy of translation is considered.

Key words: *speech message, parameters, framework, information, translation, implementation.*

Over the past 10-15 years, the nature of the work of a translator and the requirements for it have changed significantly. First of all, the changes affected the translation of scientific, technical, official and business documentation. Today it is no longer enough to simply translate a text using a computer as a typewriter. The customer expects the translator that the design of the finished document will match the appearance of the original as closely as possible, while meeting the standards accepted in the country. The translator is also required to be able to effectively use previously completed orders on the same topic, and the employer, in turn, expects significant time and cost savings when translating repetitive or similar text fragments. These strict, often contradictory conditions can only be met if the translator not only has a perfect command of the native and foreign languages and has deeply studied the subject area he has chosen, but also is confidently versed in modern computer technologies.

The key for the translator of technical documentation in these conditions is the TRANSLATION MEMORY (TM) technology. Machine translation systems have been given little space, since their capabilities are limited and this does not allow them to be recommended for use in the process of professional work on the text.

Recently, the volume of translations related to information technology has been steadily increasing, and translation and computer companies have to deal not only with the preparation of documentation, but also with the localization of software, i.e. with the translation of resources contained in exe- and dll-files. And with subsequent software testing.

What is machine translation and automated translation systems, how do they differ and how can they help a translator in his work.

Machine translate

Machine translation is the process of translating texts (written and, ideally, oral) from one natural language into another by a completely special computer program. The direction of scientific research related to the construction of such systems is also called.

Forms of organization of interaction between computers and humans in machine translation

With post-editing: the original text is processed by the machine, and the human editor corrects the result.

With pre-editing: a person adapts the text to machine processing (eliminates possible ambiguous readings, simplifies and marks up the text), after which software processing begins.

With interediting: a person interferes with the work of the translation system, resolving difficult cases.

Mixed systems (for example, simultaneously with pre- and post-editing).

Automated translation. Instead of "machine" the word automatic is sometimes used, which does not affect the meaning. However, the term automated translation has a completely different meaning - with it, the program simply helps a person translate texts.

Automated translation involves the following forms of interaction:

Partially automated translation: for example, the use of computer dictionaries by a human translator.

Systems with a division of labor: the computer is trained to translate only phrases of a rigidly defined structure (but does it in such a way that it does not need to be corrected), and gives everything that does not fit into the scheme to a person.

In English terminology, the terms of English are also distinguished. machine translation, MT (fully automatic translation) and English. machine-aided or eng. machine-assisted translation (MAT) (automated); if it is necessary to designate both, they write M(A)T.

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